

CONDITION ASSESSMENT OF FRP-STRENGTHENED CONCRETE BRIDGE DIAPHRAGMS USING NON-DESTRUCTIVE TESTING

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ABSTRACT

Carbon fibre-reinforced polymer (CFRP) materials are lightweight, corrosion-resistant composite materials extensively used to strengthen or retrofit deteriorated concrete bridge components. The retrofitting process is usually a multi-stage manual process with the inherent capability of introducing defects at the various stages of work. In this paper, a methodological approach involving various nondestructive testing (NDT) techniques has been developed for a detailed condition assessment of the state of damage in deteriorated concrete bridge diaphragms. These three diaphragms from a major Canadian bridge were externally retrofitted with multiple layers of CFRP materials and subjected to years of environmental exposure. In addition, a detailed comparison of results obtained from the NDTs and visual inspection is presented. Several issues were identified, including CFRP delamination, material incompatibility, discolouration due to corrosion, inter-fibre cracks, and fundamental problems arising from the construction of the bridge diaphragms and installation of the CFRP.

KEYWORDS

Deteriorated; retrofitting; externally bonded; condition assessment; CFRP; diaphragms

INTRODUCTION

In Canada, in 2019, more than twelve percent of publicly owned bridges were classified as either unfit for sustained service or showing increased signs of significant deterioration (CIRC, 2019). An additional twenty-six percent were categorized as being in a fair state (meaning they have exhibited signs of deterioration and deficiencies in some structural components) (CIRC, 2019). As a result, these structures generally need immediate rehabilitative or retrofitting interventions as well as mitigation of further progression of time-dependent deterioration in structural components. Traditional retrofitting schemes such as concrete section enlargement, externally bonded steel plating or external post-tensioning are often impractical due to the added self-weight or need for mechanical anchorages that can compromise the integrity of the concrete substrate. Externally bonded CFRP is an attractive solution with proven durability in harsh environmental conditions with negligible change in member size or weight. However, the strengthened substrate's short- and long-term performance relies significantly on the strength and stiffness of the bond at the CFRP-concrete interface (Karbhari & Navada, 2008), which can degrade over time due to the presence of subsurface anomalies/defects. Furthermore, in these externally bonded applications, the ongoing deterioration of the underlying concrete and at the CFRP-concrete interface is hidden behind the CFRP layer, effectively masking any visual warning signs of potential structural failure. Thus, interfacial assessment of these composite systems without compromising the bond via contact and non-contact non-destructive testing (NDT) is a critical step in assessing the structural performance of deteriorated bridge infrastructures.

Unfortunately, contrary to the condition assessment of ordinary reinforced concrete structures or composite structures (such as those used in aviation), only a few NDT techniques exist for FRP composites externally bonded to concrete structures in situ. Furthermore, while these NDT techniques are now being used in civil structures, no single method can provide comprehensive documentation of damage distribution in the composite system since each method has different advantages and

disadvantages (Karbhari et al., 2005). Moreover, the lack of unified and updated inspection qualifications, such as the National Cooperative Highway Research Program's Report 514 (Mirmiran, 2004) for their application in the condition assessment of actual concrete structures strengthened with FRP composite materials implies that assurance of their detectability (or probability of detection) and compatibility with one another relies greatly on continued laboratory research data.

In general, visual inspection is traditionally the first-level inspection approach undertaken, either localized or globally, for reinforced concrete structures. The visual inspection helps detect distress and deterioration at an earlier stage which can facilitate the repair and hence indirectly reduces the probability of failure of the structural member. However, while this condition assessment technique is relatively inexpensive and does not require specialized equipment, the limitation of the human eye and lapses in judgment implies that damages may remain unnoticed after the inspection (Yazdani et al., 2018). This is further complicated in FRP-strengthened members where signs of debonding may not be visibly detectable.

Acoustic sounding methods are perhaps the earliest NDT type adopted for CFRP-strengthened bridge inspections. This test category is traditionally performed using a coin tap or hammer. The technique generally involves knocking the surface of the composite laminate/sheets with a small coin or hammer, and a distinction in the output sound discerns a sound and unsound bond. Even though the technique is simple and cost-effective, the testing approach is inherently subjective, operator-dependent, and prone to interference from the test surroundings (e.g highway bridge). Nevertheless, demand from the aerospace industry to quantify acoustic-sounding results have led to the design of an electronic or digitized hammer tap (Halabe et al., 2020). Another advanced inspection method that has gained popularity in inspecting CFRP-strengthened bridges is infrared thermography. This technique relies on the composite system's spatial distribution of heat transfer. In principle, if there is a void or delamination within the concrete (between the CFRP strengthening layer and the substrate or within thin layers of CFRPs), then a layer of air is present that alters the material's thermal conductivity, and these anomalies can be used to locate flaws in the strengthened system (Ghosh & Karbhari, 2011; Mtenga et al., 2001; Starnes et al., 2003).

It is worth noting that in the past few decades, most research studies investigating NDT for the identification, characterization, and damage assessment of internal defects in concrete structures with externally bonded FRPs have been conducted on sound concrete with artificial defects in the laboratory (Ghosh & Karbhari, 2011; Halabe et al., 2008; Halabe et al., 2007; Mtenga et al., 2001). However, actual field conditions, including debonded regions of unknown size and location, add complexity to the detection capability of available NDT techniques such as coin tapping or infrared thermography.

(Miceli et al., 2001) demonstrated the use of infrared thermography to monitor the health of FRP bridge decks. Analysis of the infrared images revealed the usefulness of infrared thermography in detecting debonds and delamination in the FRP decks. However, surface anomalies such as staining and non-uniform wear caused complications in data interpretation. The authors also highlighted the inaccuracy of infrared thermography in estimating defects with moisture contents.

In an in-situ condition assessment, (Taillade et al., 2012) used infrared thermography to detect bonding defects on a strengthened bridge over the Doubs River in France. The bridge was built in the 1960s with three distinct and independent sections (two access spans and a main central structure). A visual inspection in the 1990s revealed extensive transverse cracking of the lower slabs on the mid-span girders, which warranted CFRP strengthening. The authors pointed out that the main challenge of the inspection was the accessibility to the FRP bonded areas. In this case, a truck-mounted lift platform was used.

While traditional coin tapping is a common inspection technique for concrete structures strengthened with CFRP, limited literature is available on the application of digital tap testing on CFRP laminates/sheets bonded to concrete structures. In a recent laboratory and field study work by (Halabe et al., 2020), findings from laboratory specimens with varying thickness shows that the digital tap

testing technique was only effective for defects at shallow depth, such as debonds in thin CFRP wraps and the technique was not able to detect delamination in thick FRP members. Moreover, their field testing results on Whiteday Bridge concrete box-beam bridge in West Virginia showed the potential of the digital tap testing technique in detecting voids and delamination in thin FRP wraps.

This paper describes the use of various NDT techniques for the condition assessment of three deteriorated concrete bridge diaphragms that were externally shear strengthened with multiple layers of CFRP materials subjected to service conditions for several years. The assessment procedure encompasses detailed visual inspection, localized NDT techniques such as tap testing (acoustic sounding), and an area scanning technique known as infrared thermography. Tapping tests were conducted using coin and the digital tap device while both a passive and active infrared thermography approach was adopted. Influential parameters that affect results and optimized procedures are discussed.

Besides the above mentioned non-intrusive condition assessment techniques of civil structures, a promising approach of capturing the development and propagation of damage is the use of distributed fibre optic sensors (DFOS) as opposed to point sensors or quasi-distributed sensors. Thus, the technology has been used to monitor various parameters ranging from temperature, vibration, force to strain variations in critical infrastructures (Jiang et al., 2010; Tan et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2006). This advanced method of continuous inspection can provide invaluable field data of strain state at debonded regions (anomalies) in CFRP retrofitted structures. The general principles that govern the application of fibre optic sensors in intelligent and resilient structures are summarized in literature (Mufti, 2002; Tennyson et al., 2001; Watkins et al., 2007).

Overview of the bridge and its environmental exposure conditions

The three strengthened diaphragms were obtained from a bridge superstructure with a highly integrated structural system comprised of precast post-tensioned concrete girders joined together by cast-in-place infill slabs and lateral load resisting members (diaphragms that were transversely post-tensioned). As a result of significant corrosion-induced deterioration, several portions of the bridge were strengthened with CFRP sheets at various intervals throughout the structure's service life. During service, the structure was exposed to harsh environmental conditions that are detrimental to the short- and long-term durability of the composite strengthening schemes. The annual climate varies from warm-humid summers to several months of freezing winter. Multiple freeze-thaw cycles and excessive use of deicing salt in the winter months are common for structures in this region of Canada.

Most of the CFRP repair works on the bridge were undertaken to improve the shear capacity of girders and diaphragms. The shear strengthening configuration on the retrofitted components mainly employed vertical U-wraps in two layers (the sheets are continuous around the member's bottom) with horizontal strips (additional two layers) at the top and bottom providing anchorage (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Schematic of CFRP shear strengthened diaphragms and dimensions

Composite strengthening work on these three diaphragms was achieved with flexible CFRP sheets through a wet lay-up process. Each diaphragm was strengthened with six double-layer vertical strips with a width of approximately 305 mm and a CFRP strip spacing ranging from 135 mm to 150 mm. Thickness of the strips (two layers) extracted for coupon testing was estimated between 3.2 mm to 3.5

mm. The average thickness of the actual concrete diaphragms ranged from 210 mm (for diaphragm 2) to 220 mm (for diaphragms 1 and 3), each weighing approximately 4.2 metric tons. A typical post-tensioned diaphragm was reinforced with five internal post-tensioning tendons unevenly distributed along their height, each comprised of 12 strands with diameters of 7 mm. These tendons were horizontally placed; hence, their contribution to shear capacity was achieved indirectly through axial compression in the concrete.

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

Methodology for non-destructive condition assessment

Visual Inspection

In this study, visual inspection was the first step in the condition assessment for all three diaphragms. To access both surfaces of each diaphragm, two 50 mm diameter holes were drilled approximately 750 mm from the soffit of the diaphragms in the concrete strip to facilitate lifting by overhead crane. During the visual inspection, a cloud-based inspection tool equipped with artificial intelligence (AI) crack detection capability was used to record defective spots. This record keeping method allows the specification of defect locations on the diaphragms, the size of the observed defect, the type of damage and its severity.

Acoustic Sounding

The coin tapping technique is a conventional acoustic testing method used to locate subsurface defects (delamination or voids) in thin composite materials. A coin was used to impact the surface of the CFRP wraps on the diaphragms as shown Figure 2. The debonds were then marked and the location and estimation of the area of delamination on the CFRP strips for a given surface was recorded and sketched.

Figure 2 Traditional coin tapping between stitches of individual fibres

The entire surface of each strip of CFRP was completely coin tapped a minimum of four times per strip. The procedure generally involved tapping on and between individual stitches of fibres on the strips. While this approach was extremely time consuming, it did prove to be an efficient method for pinpointing smaller defects. The coin tapping technique was also used to locate delamination in the concrete, especially at critical locations such as the diaphragm-girder joints.

Infrared Thermography

Infrared thermography (IRT) was then conducted using FLIR high resolution (640 x 480) T650sc handheld infrared camera and the heater shown on the right image of Figure 3. This T650sc system operates in the 7.5-14 μm long-wavelength. The camera is equipped with the ability to save the radiometric images (images of temperature values in each pixel) which can then be post-processed using the company's propriety software such as the researchIR or FLIR tools.

Figure 3 T650sc camera from FLIR and the portable heating source used

The T650sc used in this research had a sensitivity of less than 0.002 Celsius with an operational temperature range of minus 15 degrees Celsius to 50 degrees Celsius. The heating technique used in this research involved four 1500 watts ceiling heaters that were connected in series on a wooden frame and mounted on a crane system (Figure 4).

Figure 4 Heating lamps connected in series

This heating setup helped maintain a fixed distance between the lamps and CFRP surface while also allowing the flexibility to adjust the distance between the heating source and the CFRP surface. The distance ranged from 300 mm for concrete only regions to a maximum of 1 m for the CFRP bonded surfaces. To provide uniform heating, the mounted heating system was first positioned along the length of each individual strip and later moved across the length of the diaphragms to capture the entire surface area. The heating durations of the strips was set to 60 seconds and 120 seconds. Data acquisition was initiated as soon as the heaters were crane-lifted a substantial distance above the strip or totally removed from the surface of the diaphragm. It is worth pointing out that prior to implementing the heating technique mentioned above, previous efforts to use heating blankets or passive heating while the components were stored outdoors presented several challenges and did not produce reliable results.

Digital tap testing

To cross check the results from the conventional tap testing and the IRT, an automated acoustic sounding approach using the digital tap hammer in Figure 5 was also conducted on the defects located by the traditional coin tap and the IRT. This low-cost instrumented hammer provides a quantitative measurement of the hammer impact pulse duration in microseconds on a display screen. The procedure involves tapping a sound area (defect-free) and any tap value greater than 10 percent of the values obtained for those of the sound area is classified as a defect region. In this research, a minimum of ten taps were performed on sound areas of the bonded CFRP area and thereafter, known defects identified by the traditional coin tap test and the IRT were tapped using the digital hammer to confirm the results.

Figure 5 Digital tapping device

It is worth noting that the sensor at the tip of digital tap hammer is very sensitive to hard impact or surfaces which makes the digital tap testing a perfect fit for inspection of FRP-only materials as used in the aerospace industry.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Visual Inspection findings

The visual inspection revealed similar types of defects for each diaphragm, although their severity varied. The issues ranged from material compatibility between the underlying concrete and the patch mortar (Figure 6), delamination of bonded composites (Figure 7), discolouration due to corrosion products (Figure 9), damage likely caused during transportation (scratches on CFRP strips as depicted in Figure 10), and other minor blemishes (Figure 10). Construction issues (such as random placement of rebars shown in Figure 8) were also noted.

Bond issues between the underlying concrete substrate and the patch mortar were visible from the saw-cut edges of the diaphragms (Figure 6). In some instances, severe cracks at the concrete-mortar interface or a total delamination at the interface was observed. Initiation and propagation of such defects means that the force transfer between the composite and the concrete is compromised. The use of multiple patch materials at the same location was also noticed in the other diaphragms which may exacerbate the delamination process due to incompatibilities between disparate materials.

Figure 6 Typical mortar-concrete bond issues

The most detrimental issue from the perspective of structural performance that was visible in all three inspected diaphragms prior to NDT was delamination of the CFRP strips from the concrete (Figure 7) that was visible at the edges of the diaphragms. The extent of the delamination was later verified through NDT.

Figure 7 Interfacial delamination between CFRP and substrate

Figure 8 shows steel reinforcing bars either overlapping each other or placed without any concrete cover. In this scenario, the corrosion of one rebar will inevitably extend to the nearby reinforcement. Rebars placed too close to the surface without concrete cover would lead to accelerated corrosion leading to surface cracking that could compromise the integrity of the CFRP-concrete bond.

Figure 8 Reinforcing bars placed next to each other or placed without concrete

Some rust-coloured discolouration was observed in the excess epoxy paste for Diaphragm #3 (Figure 9), although its location does not seem to be caused by a reinforcing rebar or tendon.

Figure 9 Diaphragm #3 showing corrosion product on both sides of the diaphragm

Furthermore, none of the diaphragms showed any signs of sagging of strips at the soffit that are common in overhead installations. However, excessive resins that were not rolled out cured as hard bubbles on multiple vertical strips at the chamfered corners of all the diaphragms as depicted in Figure 10. While at first glance these defects are indeed benign aesthetic blemishes, they result from the excessive use of primers which may cause low stress transfer between the composite and the concrete. In a bond-critical application such as the retrofitting work on these diaphragms, intimate bond through low thickness of primer should be maintained between the concrete and the CFRP material. Figure 10 also displays benign flaws or blemishes that likely occurred during the transportation of the diaphragms. These scratches are believed to have negligible impact on the strength and stiffness of the composite material, although a severe scratch introduced by lifting equipment could severely compromise the contribution from the composite material.

Figure 10 a & b) Excessive resins that cured as bubbles c) transportation scratches

A unique problem to diaphragm #1 was a 340-mm long crack in one of the CFRP vertical strips oriented parallel to the fibres (Figure 11). It is unknown when this crack was initiated in the composite material.

Figure 11 Crack running in the fibre direction (highlighted in red)

In the concrete, severe cracks were observed at the joint between the diaphragm and the girder which may have been initiated by the corrosion of the reinforcing tendons (Figure 12 and Figure 13). The minor horizontal cracks branching from the major cracks seen in Figure 12 could lead to interfacial delamination at the CFRP-concrete interface and a subsequent delamination of the detached concrete portion. Most cracks on the sides of the diaphragms (girder-diaphragm joints) were picked up by the AI crack detection software used for the crack inspection (Figure 12); however, the software failed to reveal cracks in the concrete located between the CFRP strips that were visible to naked eyes. A magnifying glass was also used but did not identify additional surface cracks.

In one of the girder-diaphragm joints in diaphragm #2, the cracks extended 1.5 m along the length of the joint (Figure 13) subsequently leading to the total delamination of the top anchorage strip.

Figure 12 A major crack at the joint between diaphragm #1 and adjacent girder detected by INSPECT

Figure 13 1.5 m crack at the cold joint between diaphragm 2 and the adjacent girder

Acoustic Sounding and Infrared Thermography

Findings from the acoustic sounding and infrared thermography (Figure 14 and Figure 15) are presented in this subsequent section. A sketch of the size and location of the localized delaminated areas identified by the conventional coin tapping method are shown schematically in Figure 16 (the combined plots for both infrared results and conventional tap test).

In an environment with relatively low noise levels such as the structural laboratory in which the NDT were conducted, the conventional coin tapping test was found to be very efficient in locating subsurface defects within the CFRP wraps. Estimation of the percentage of defective area on the bonded CFRP regions shows a value of 1.5 and 1.4% for surface I and surface II of Diaphragm #1, 2.8 and 0.8% for surfaces I and II of Diaphragm #2, and 2.2 and 1.2% for surface 1 and II of Diaphragm #3, respectively. These values show that only a small fraction of the total bonded area in all three diaphragms were detached from the concrete substrate and that most of the total bonded area are in good condition. The plots of Figure 16 show that the delamination issues on the diaphragms as detected by the conventional coin tapping tended to be concentrated on the anchorage (horizontal) strips mainly near the soffit of the diaphragms and edge strips. A better understanding of how these defects compromise the bond performance of the strengthened diaphragms will be further investigated during the destructive testing phase of work.

Infrared thermography

It is worth noting that the initial passive infrared inspection conducted on all three diaphragms at an outdoor storage site in Ottawa in winter did not reveal any defects. This result is attributed to the low ambient temperature since no external excitation of heat was possible. In other words, these elements were in a state of thermal equilibrium at the outside storage site. However, in the lab, infrared thermography was able to diagnose debonding problems that went unnoticed by the conventional coin tapping (Figure 15 and Figure 16).

Figure 14 Digital and thermal images of a typical defect in a CFRP strip

Figure 15 Debonds detected by infrared thermography on anchorage strips

Figure 16 Diaphragm #1 surface 1 (left) and surface 2 (right)

■ Debonds detected by coin tapping
 ■ Debonds detected by Infrared
 ■ Debonds detected by both methods

Since the method relies on differential heat flow within the materials with high sensitivity to voids, defects within the vertical shear strengthening strips that were undetectable by the coin tap either due to size or stiffness of the defective area were found using the infrared thermography approach (Figure 16). Results obtained from both the conventional coin tapping and infrared shows that both methods should compliment each other in any composite inspection work. A good agreement between the coin tapping and infrared was observed for diaphragm #1 and diaphragm #3, while for diaphragm #2 surface II a major difference was noticed.

The additional defects that were discovered through the infrared method ranged from 0.5 percent for surface I of diaphragm #2 to 4.1 percent for surface II of the same diaphragm. This discrepancy between the infrared and coin tapping for diaphragm #2 may have occurred due to the sensitivity of the infrared camera in capturing any slight variation in heat transfer between sound and unsound regions, whereas the coin tapping is subjective and more sensitive to local stiffness of the defective area. If a significant portion of concrete is attached to a defective area, then it would be challenging for the coin tap to give an accurate distinctive sound upon tapping. The infrared results also confirmed the debonding issues in the anchorage strips that were observed during the coin tapping test.

During the inspection of the bridge diaphragms, the benefits of this modern inspection technique such as its ability to scan a large surface area within a very short period compared to other available test methods was noticeable. The technique was highly repeatable and is labour efficient. The infrared testing method allowed the flexibility to quickly locate and estimate the total delaminated area. Nevertheless, the infrared also suffers some disadvantages. A key limitation of the technique is that in instances where the depth of the defects is of concern, the infrared camera only provides information on voids' planar dimensions. On the other hand, its sensitivity to temperature variation means depending on the heat intensity, defects can be left undetected. Other disadvantages that could affect the infrared results such as non-uniform heating, reflections from test surroundings, and the quality of the camera were taken into consideration during the inspection of the diaphragms.

Due to lack of base line data on the material properties of the composite used to strengthened the bridge diaphragms in this research project, a key experimental work prior to the infrared thermography should have included the determination of the glass transition temperature (T_g).

Digital Tap Testing

The digital tap testing method proved to be a quick and convenient technique for assessing the condition of externally bonded CFRP sheets. This technique was used to recheck the defects that were detected by the coin tap and infrared thermography method. The digital tap test was inconsistent in verifying defective spots within the regions previously identified by the coin tapping or infrared thermography. The infrared and conventional tapping test can be used as standalone condition assessment techniques for concrete structures retrofitted with CFRP composite materials. The same cannot be said for the digital tap test that was developed to test FRP-only materials. Although coin tapping has its inherent drawback, a more time efficient approach for inspection of large composite structures strengthened with CFRP composites should start with coin tap testing since the method can help narrow down the defective area and the accuracy of the result can be checked by both the digital tap test and infrared thermography. The condition assessment of these bridge diaphragms confirms the consensus that the digital tap test is generally challenging to detect delamination in thick members. The technique was found to be sensitive to the local stiffness of the defective area.

CONCLUSION

This paper summarizes the findings from a detailed condition assessment of deteriorated CFRP retrofitted concrete diaphragms. Common discontinuities, such as cracks, and material incompatibility were identified during the visual inspections. Subsurface defects were located using acoustic sounding and infrared thermography. Various criteria were considered in selecting the various NDT to primarily optimize the estimation of debond area in the composite retrofitting work. The acoustic-sounding methods, for instance were chosen based on the following criteria:

- Its capability to detect localized flaws without interference from environmental conditions or thermal effects.
- Availability of testing devices and practicality in in-situ inspections
- Real-time data interpretation without the need for trained personnel

The infrared thermography, on the other hand was chosen to close the limitations inherent in the acoustic testing methods, such as the lack of sensitivity of the acoustic technique in identifying more minor defects. Further consideration includes:

- The capability to globally identify defects in the composite in a time-efficient manner
- High level of sensitivity to the presence of anomalies in the composite.

Based on the detailed condition assessment in this study, the following conclusions can be drawn with regards to the use of NDTs for inspection of full-size FRP-strengthened concrete elements:

- Similar types of defects for each diaphragm were detected, although their severity varied.
- A strong bond between CFRP and concrete still exists in these diaphragms after extensive exposure to harsh environmental conditions in-service.
- Defects are concentrated around anchorage strips.
- Detailed field inspections aiming to assess the state of damage in FRP repair would require multiple complementary NDT techniques.
- NDT results for CFRP-strengthened concrete substrate can be limited to in-plane estimations and discerning the depth of defect would require semi-destructive field test such as the direct tension pull-off test that can allow for the determination of both the strength of the bond and the specific layer in the multi-layer composite where deterioration will initiate failure.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest in creating this research paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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